

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

Data Repositories and Certification in a Diverse Trust Landscape

Results of SSHOC T8.2
Desk Research

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Data Repositories and Certification in a Diverse Trust Landscape: Results of SSHOC T8.2 Desk Research

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Abstract: The report analyses the results of desk research on SSHOC data repositories conducted to examine the typology of repositories and explore the role of certification and applicability of CoreTrustSeal to SSHOC organisations.

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Executive Summary

This report forms part of the overall body of work conducted by the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) Task 8.2 team. One of the objectives of this task was to examine the trust landscape of organisations participating in the SSHOC project and from the wider Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain.

As part of SSHOC Task 8.2, desk research was conducted in the autumn of 2021. The aim of this research was to explore the SSHOC trust landscape and examine the applicability of CoreTrustSeal Trusted Digital Repository (TDR) certification for repositories belonging to one of the four SSHOC member ERICs (European Research Infrastructure Consortiums). Areas that were examined within the desk research include repository type and stability, certification status, repository and research data discovery and identification, and the provision of repository information made available to users and other stakeholders.

The results of this research indicate that TDR certification plays an important role in enhancing repository practice, particularly in relation to the provision of repository information to users and stakeholders. TDR certification appears to be closely related to ERIC membership within the SSHOC community, which in turn impacts on several areas relating to repository best practice. Differences that were noted between certified and non-certified repositories in our sample include the use of persistent identifiers, repository registry use and approach to digital preservation.

The results also highlight significant variation in the terminology used by SSHOC repositories to refer to repository services and/or service components. Areas of terminological variation that were noted during the desk research include (but are not limited to) designated communities (and their related entities and/or stakeholders), disciplinary specialism and sub-specialism and the type(s) of data stored by repositories. Such terminological differences within the SSH domain creates challenges for TDR certification and the possible certification of wider data service providers.

Further work is needed to examine the various characteristics of data repositories and data service providers within the SSH community and the wider European preservation landscape. Additional areas of focus that such work could address include possible certification solutions for SSH repositories and data service providers as well as the applicability of such solutions to the wider European digital preservation landscape.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
PID	Persistent Identifier
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
TDR	Trusted Digital Repository
URN	Uniform Resource Name

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1. Introduction

As part of Work Package 8 (*Governance, Sustainability and Quality Assurance*) of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project¹, the Task 8.2 team conducted a piece of desk research examining the various characteristics of SSHOC organisations and repositories. The aim of the desk research was to gain insight into how the CoreTrustSeal applies to SSHOC organisations and repositories, alongside the role that certification plays within the wider SSHOC landscape. An additional goal was to examine the typology of repositories and data service providers. The desk research took place between July 2021 and September 2021 and was conducted by visiting the websites of selected SSHOC repositories and collecting information on the 28 features relating to CoreTrustSeal certification. All organisational characteristics examined are listed in Appendix 1.

The organisations were selected based on a list of potential candidates for certification support from SSHOC who were members of one of four European Research Infrastructure Consortiums (ERICs): the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA), the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN), the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) and the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS). The list of 124 entities was purposively compiled during the planning of the certification support element of Task 8.2 in September 2020 (see *D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories*²). Another ten relevant organisations were added to the list before commencing the desk research.

Out of the final list of 134 entities, 41 were excluded from the analysis because they did not qualify as data repositories according to Task 8.2's definition of a repository, that is, "organisations that preserve, manage, and provide access to digital research data in a variety of formats"³. The primary reason for the organisation not meeting the above definition was that it did not appear to preserve or manage digital research data and/or provide access to data (e.g. via metadata listed in a public data catalogue). Examples of such organisations included search registries, research foundations, institutes (of varying descriptions), amongst others.

The reason for initial identification of these organisations as potential candidates for the desk research was due to the sampling method employed (purposive sampling) which involved using the membership lists of the aforementioned ERICs as a way of identifying organisations that could be included in the research. All of the 'non-repositories' that were subsequently excluded from our analysis were members

¹ SSHOC Project: <https://sshopencloud.eu/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

² Kleemola et al. 2020.

³ Ibid.

of either E-RIHS⁴ or DARIAH⁵, with 9 of the 39 DARIAH organisations and 32 of the 43 E-RIHS organisations being subsequently excluded. This confusion over what is a digital repository compared to, say, a data service provider also occurred in the responses received to a separate survey conducted as part of SSHOC T8.2.⁶ In this instance, a number of respondents were from wider service providers such as registries or research foundations.

Nevertheless, the research and subsequent analysis detailed within this report is based on information collected from the 93 repositories that meet the above criteria.

⁴ E-RIHS: <http://www.e-rihs.eu/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

⁵ DARIAH-EU: <https://www.dariah.eu/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

⁶ Ala-Lahti et al. 2022.

2. Results

2.1 Geographical Distribution, Types and Stability of Repositories

The repositories in our sample were located in 27 different countries. One repository was in the USA and the rest were spread across 26 European countries (see figure 1). The geographical distribution of repositories was not uniform, with 34% of repositories in our sample being in either Italy, Germany or France. Poland and Slovenia were also well-represented with six repositories each. Western European repositories were better represented in our sample than Eastern European ones, which is a consequence of the purposive method of selection. However, it should be noted that the aim of the desk research was not to achieve a representative sample of all European repositories. Out of the 93 repositories in our sample, 20 were affiliated with CESSDA, 24 with CLARIN, 30 with DARIAH, and 12 with E-RHIS. Seven repositories were unaffiliated with ERICs.

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of the examined repositories in Europe (n=92).

Over three quarters of repositories in our sample were hosted by a larger organisation – in most cases a university (43%). Other host organisations included research institutes, academies and ministries. It was not always clear whether a repository was part of another organisation and how it was situated within it. In some cases, the information sought through desk research was available from the host organisation but not the repository itself.

Using the CoreTrustSeal typology, the repositories were assigned a ‘type’ based on the information available on the repository’s website. More than one type could be assigned to a repository. Domain or subject-based repositories were the most common type, with 77% of our sample being classified as such (see figure 2). Institutional repositories made up one fifth of our sample, followed by national repositories (14% of our overall sample). Only a handful of repositories in our sample were classified as alternate type

of repository.⁷ Whilst it is possible that the repositories might assign themselves a different typology, it became apparent during the desk research that a large number of repositories in our sample referred to themselves as a domain or subject-based repository.

Figure 2. Repository type in the CoreTrustSeal typology. More than one type could be assigned to a single repository (n=93). Percentages were rounded up.

A simpler categorization that was also utilised in the desk research was specialist and generalist repositories, which is in keeping with the CoreTrustSeal typology. 83% of repositories in our sample were categorised as being a specialist repository and 17% as Generalist. Again, it is possible that some of the repositories might classify themselves differently, but it was clear from the desk research that the majority of repositories met the criteria required to be classed as a specialist repository.

The specialist repositories were represented by various fields in the social sciences, humanities, linguistics, culture and arts (see table 1). There were also a number of repositories that stored data from

⁷ Other types of repository according to the CoreTrustSeal typology include: Library, Museum or Archive; Research project repository; Other

outside of the realm of SSH, with a number of repositories storing life science(s) data. It was noted during the desk research that there was a wide variation in the terminology used by repositories when referring to their area(s) of specialism. The primary source of this information (and the terminology used by the repositories) was the repositories' mission statements. However, the exact terminology used to describe the specialisms is not reported here to avoid identifying highly specialised repositories. In keeping with the proportion of CESSDA, CLARIN and DARIAH repositories, 80% of the specialist repositories represented social sciences, linguistics and humanities (see table 1 below).

Category	Areas of specialism included in category	Percentage of total number of specialist repositories
Social Sciences	<i>Sociology, Politics, Social Medicine, Social statistics, Economics, Anthropology</i>	26%
Humanities	<i>History, Archaeology</i>	22%
Linguistics	<i>Computational Linguistics, Natural Language, Corpuses, Speech Technology, Psycholinguistics</i>	32%
Culture	<i>Regional studies, Cultural Heritage, Media and Film, Drama and Theatre, Literature, Musicology</i>	13%
Arts	<i>Fine Art, Graphic Design</i>	4%
Other	<i>Biomedical, Genetics, Epidemiology, Psychology, Life Sciences</i>	3%

Table 1. Categorisation of specialisms amongst specialist repositories (n=77). Percentages were rounded up.

The data types preserved by repositories in our sample was also examined. The type(s) of data stored varied a great deal between the repositories, although some commonalities could be identified between repositories according to ERIC membership, but even then, variation was significant.

The members of CESSDA primarily preserved quantitative social science data (particularly survey data), text and images, while the members of CLARIN mainly stored language data, as well as resources and tools such as corpora, lexicons, audiovisual data and text. For repositories belonging to DARIAH, the most common data type was textual data, but several also stored audio, video, images and multimedia data. The most common data type for the members of E-RIHS was images, but there was more variation in the data types stored by E-RIHS repositories compared to the repositories from the other three ERICs. Other types of data stored by repositories in our sample included bibliographic records and catalogue information of physical objects, alongside metadata for various monographs, research outputs and digital and/or physical documents.

Most of the repositories in our sample explicitly stated who they considered to be their designated community. In the event that they did not, it could nearly always be inferred from either their mission statement and/or the information provided on the repositories' websites. The table presented in appendix 2 provides a categorisation of the designated communities listed by repositories in our sample and the terminology used to describe said designated communities. Despite our small sample size, there were 62 different terms used to describe the different designated communities, their members and other

related entities and/or stakeholders. The 'research community' was the most common designated community cited. Other designated communities and/or entities cited by repositories in our sample included national governments and political parties, private enterprises, the general public, educational institutions, independent professionals and media organisations and journalists. Some repositories provided their services to multiple communities, with all repositories in our sample stating that they served at least two different designated communities.

The number of designated communities and/or entities cited by the repositories in our sample illustrates the plurality of opinion as to what constitutes a designated community and the difficulty in defining what constitutes a designated community and the entities that comprise said community. This indicates that further work is needed to reach a consensus on what constitutes a designated community.⁸

Changes in repository name and URLs since the sample was first compiled in September 2020 were recorded in order to examine the persistence of repositories. For the newer repositories in our sample, the stability of names and URLs was examined using either the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine⁹ or domain tools such as WhoIs Lookup¹⁰. Over 90% of the repositories had retained their names and URLs, but for 8% of them there had been a change in either the name, URL or both (see figure 3). The results indicate that the majority of the repositories were persistent over the short observation period, but the fact that nearly one tenth had changed either their URL, name or both points to the inevitability of change in the repository landscape. It also highlights the need for adequate use of repository identifiers and registry listings by the SSH community.

⁸ The concept of the designated community of TDRs is discussed in L'Hours et al. (2022) which is a working paper authored by members of the SSHOC, EOSC Nordic and FAIRsFAIR projects.

⁹ Internet Archive - Wayback Machine: <https://archive.org/web/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹⁰ Whois (DomainTools): <https://whois.domaintools.com/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

Figure 3. Changes in repository names and URLs since September 2020 (n=93). Percentages were rounded up.

The year the repositories were established, the size of their holdings and their full-time equivalent were also examined in the desk research. However, it became apparent that this information was not readily available in most cases, thus making comparison difficult. This result is not unexpected as digital data repositories are a relatively new phenomenon.¹¹ This can also be seen in the years the repositories were established, as 43% of repositories in the sample were established between 2010 and 2019, 18% were established between 2000 and 2009, 8% were established between 1990 and 1999, and 10% were established prior to 1990. A handful, 3%, were established in 2020 or later. It was not possible to ascertain the year of establishment for the remaining 18%.

¹¹ See, for example, Doorn & Tjalsma 2007.

Figure 4. Years that the repositories were established (n=93). Percentages were rounded up.

Information on the number of studies or objects in the repository holdings was available for the majority of the repositories (76%) but owing to the differing data types and items preserved, comparisons are not feasible. The numbers of digital objects ranged from eight datasets to hundreds of corpora (containing billions of tokens) to thousands or hundreds of thousands of bibliographic records or entries. In addition, information on the total file sizes of the holdings was only available for seven repositories. The FTE number of staff employed by the repositories in our sample was generally not available, but information on the number of staff could be found listed on 38% of the repository websites. The number of staff employed ranged from 1–309. However, despite obtaining this information, it was not sufficient to allow for a comparison of available resources amongst the repositories in our sample, as we were unable to ascertain whether these were full-time or part-time staff.

2.2 Certification Status

Over half of the repositories in our sample (56%) did not have TDR certification (or at least the information about certification was not readily available on their websites). Amongst the certified repositories, the most common certification was the CoreTrustSeal, with 90% of certified repositories in our sample possessing it (figure 5). This was to be expected as the CoreTrustSeal is a core certification for Trustworthy Digital Repositories preserving data in the long term, with some ERICs requiring member organisations to be CTS certified. The CLARIN certificate B was the second most common, and it was awarded to nearly all CLARIN repositories on the list. A little over a third of the certified repositories had been awarded other certificates such as the ISO27001, CLARIN B, Europeana Accreditation or some other type of international or national certification.

There was significant overlap in certification, as nearly all the repositories with the CLARIN B certificate also had the CoreTrustSeal. Most of the repositories with another type of certification also had either the CoreTrustSeal or the CLARIN B certificate.

Figure 5. Share of certificates among the certified repositories (n=41). The repositories could have more than one certification. Percentages were rounded up.

Furthermore, Table 2 below examines certification type according to ERIC membership. Nearly all of the CLARIN repositories and over half of the CESSDA repositories had some form of TDR certification, whereas less than a fifth of DARIAH repositories and even fewer unaffiliated repositories had some form of TDR certification (see table 2 below). None of the E-RIHS repositories in our sample had any form of TDR certification, which is most likely because the E-RIHS is a new ERIC that is expected to enter the

operational phase in 2022.¹² Most of the repositories that had CoreTrustSeal certification were members of either CLARIN or CESSDA. This was somewhat expected as CoreTrustSeal certification is an obligation for CESSDA Service Providers and all service-providing CLARIN centres need to obtain the CLARIN B certificate, which requires the applicant to have at least initiated the CoreTrustSeal application procedure.¹³

	CESSDA repositories (n=20)	CLARIN repositories (n=24)	DARIAH repositories (n=30)	E-RIHS repositories (n=12)	Unaffiliated repositories (n=7)
Percentage of repositories with at least one form of TDR certification	60% (in total)	96% (in total)	17% (in total)	0% (in total)	14% (in total)
Percentage of repositories with CoreTrustSeal	60%	92%	10%	0%	0%
Percentage of repositories with another form of TDR certification*	35%	96%	13%	0%	14%

Table 2. Breakdown of certification by infrastructure membership. Percentages were rounded up. *In some cases, repositories had both the CoreTrustSeal, alongside another type of TDR certification; thus, the percentages in the second and third row are independent of each other.

The results relayed in table 2 are somewhat unsurprising given the selection method used, which resulted in our sample being composed mainly of European partner organisations, for many of whom the CoreTrustSeal has become the standard form of TDR certification. Other forms of TDR certification were distributed more evenly among the ERICs, except for CLARIN repositories. In this instance, CLARIN repositories who had an alternative form of TDR certification were nearly always in possession of the CLARIN B certificate.

¹² E-RIHS milestones: <http://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-progress-state/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹³ Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) 2017; Trust - CESSDA: <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Working-Groups/Trust> [accessed 9 February 2022]; CLARIN - Assessment Procedure: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/assessment-procedure> [accessed 9 February 2022]

2.3 Discoverability of Repositories and Data

Research data, databases and the organisations providing them and other data services are numerous and can be challenging for researchers to find. Registries have been set up to facilitate the discovery of data repositories, along with registries for data discovery and related resources. Notable repository registries include re3data¹⁴ (Registry of Research Data Repositories), FAIRsharing¹⁵, and ROR¹⁶ (Research Organization Registry).

Over half of the repositories in our sample (57%) had a re3data profile and just under half of our sample (49%) had a ROR profile (see figure 6). In some cases, the information available on ROR was about the hosting organisation instead of the repository itself. Significantly fewer repositories in our sample (10%) had a FAIRsharing record, with all of them being social science data repositories. Our sample's overall representation on repository registries is promising, with 82% of our sample being listed on at least one of the registries mentioned. Some repositories in our sample had a record/profile on more than one repository registry, with 22% of repositories being listed on two of the three repository registries and 6% of repositories being listed on all three repository registries (54% of our sample were listed on one of the registries and 8% were not listed on any of the three).

¹⁴ Re3data: www.re3data.org [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹⁵ FAIRsharing: <https://fairsharing.org/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

¹⁶ ROR: <https://ror.org/> [accessed 9 February 2022]

Figure 6. Repository information available on re3data, FAIRsharing and ROR (n=93). Percentages were rounded up. Some of the repositories had a record/profile on more than one registry. The columns are therefore independent of each other and do not make up an overall total.

Taking a closer look at the breakdown of repositories, it is apparent that the CESSDA and CLARIN repositories were predominantly listed on re3data, whilst DARIAH and E-RIHS repositories tended to have ROR profiles instead (see table 3). All of the CLARIN repositories and 85% of the CESSDA repositories had a re3data profile, while one out of five DARIAH repositories and one out of six E-RIHS repositories had one.

When it comes to ROR, the E-RIHS repositories dominated with three quarters having a ROR profile. More than half of the DARIAH repositories had a profile on ROR, while roughly a third of CESSDA and CLARIN repositories had one. There was only a slight difference between the number of re3data and ROR profiles for unaffiliated repositories, and the overlap between the unaffiliated repositories with more than one profile was notable. The handful of repositories with FAIRsharing records were mostly members of CESSDA.

	CESSDA repositories (n=20)	CLARIN repositories (n=24)	DARIAH repositories (n=30)	E-RIHS repositories (n=12)	Unaffiliated repositories (n=7)
Percentage of repositories with a re3data profile	85%	100%	20%	17%	75%
Percentage of repositories with a ROR profile	35%	33%	57%	75%	71%
Percentage of repositories with a FAIRsharing record	35%	0%	3%	0%	14%

Table 3. Percentages of repositories with re3data and ROR profiles and FAIRsharing records by research infrastructure. Percentages were rounded up. Some of the repositories had profiles/records on more than one registry. The three rows are therefore independent of each other.

There appeared to be a connection between registry listing and certification status. All of the certified repositories in our sample had a profile/record on at least one of the repository registries, whilst the same was true for only two thirds of the non-certified repositories (table 4). A closer look at the overall distribution of registry listings within our sample suggests that the differences observed can be explained by the high share of certified repositories with a re3data record. When it comes to ROR profiles, slightly more non-certified repositories have a ROR profile compared to certified repositories. Although only a handful of repositories had a FAIRsharing record, the difference between certified and non-certified repositories is also evident (see table 4 below).

	Certified (n=41)	Not certified (n=52)
Percentage of repositories with any repository record	100%	67%
Percentage of repositories with a re3data profile	95%	27%
Percentage of repositories with a ROR profile	44%	54%
Percentage of repositories with a FAIRsharing record	17%	4%

Table 4. Shares of certified and non-certified repositories with re3data, ROR and FAIRsharing record. Percentages were rounded up. Some of the repositories had profiles/records on more than one registry. The rows are therefore independent of each other.

The desk research also sought to examine how much of the information on re3data was up to date by cross-referencing the information on the repositories' re3data profiles against the information provided on their websites. The results were recorded using a three-point rating scale (see figure 7), with the aim of providing an overall indication of the persistence and discoverability of the repositories in our sample. The persistence and discoverability of repositories is important as it is expected that active repositories update their information on discovery services regularly. Whilst the ratings are subjective, all or most of the information was up to date for more than half of the repositories (figure 7). Some information was outdated for 42% of the repositories, and one repository was missing all or nearly all of the recent information. The share of repositories not providing up-to-date information on re3data indicates that active metadata curation is needed and repositories should pay more attention to maintaining their records. The importance of registries as "essential components of the FAIR data ecosystem" is noted, for instance, in the report and action plan by the European Commission expert group on FAIR data.¹⁷

¹⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2018.

Figure 7. Estimate of how much of the information on re3data was up to date (n=53). Percentages were rounded up.

Persistent identifiers are crucial in enabling data discovery, linking, identification and citation. 54% of repositories in our sample used one PID system and a further 11% of our sample used two or more PID systems (the total number of repositories in our using at least one PID system was therefore 65%).

Among the repositories using at least one PID system, the most common one was Handle, which was used by 62% of repositories, followed by DOI which was used by 43% of repositories with a PID system in use (figure 8). Only a handful of repositories in our sample used alternative PID systems (either in conjunction with the above PID systems or in isolation). The prevalence of Handle is mainly due to their popularity among the CLARIN repositories in our sample and to a lesser extent, the DARIAH repositories. DOI, on the other hand, was primarily used by the CESSDA repositories in our sample.

Figure 8. Shares of persistent identifiers in repositories using at least one PID (n=60). Some repositories used more than one PID. Percentages were rounded up.

ERIC membership also appeared to be connected to the use of PID systems, with all CLARIN repositories and the 85% of CESSDA repositories in our sample using at least one PID system (table 5), whereas just over half (57%) of the unaffiliated repositories made use of a PID system. Surprisingly, even fewer repositories that were members of either DARIAH or E-RIHS used a PID system (40% of DARIAH repositories and 25% of E-RIHS repositories).

	CESSDA repositories (n=20)	CLARIN repositories (n=24)	DARIAH repositories (n=30)	E-RIHS repositories (n=12)	Unaffiliated repositories (n=7)
Percentage of repositories with a persistent identifier	85%	100%	40%	25%	57%

Table 5. Breakdown of repositories using at least one persistent identifier by infrastructure membership. Percentages were rounded up.

The prevalence of PID use amongst the certified repositories in our sample is also clear, with nearly all of the certified repositories in our sample (95%) using at least one PID system compared to only 40% of non-certified repositories (see table 6). CoreTrustSeal-certified repositories are expected to use at least

one PID system for their stored data and metadata, which is addressed in Requirement 13 on ‘Data discovery and Identification’.¹⁸ The use of a PID system is also a requirement for CLARIN B centres¹⁹ and CESSDA equally expects its Service Providers to “use globally unique PID to identify their data holdings”²⁰. This, coupled with the aforementioned conditions for CESSDA repositories and CLARIN B centres regarding CoreTrustSeal certification, could also help explain the differences in the use of PID systems amongst the repositories in our sample.

	Certified (n=41)	Not certified (n=52)
Percentage of repositories with a persistent identifier	95%	40%

Table 6. Shares of certified and non-certified repositories using at least one persistent identifier. Percentages were rounded up.

2.4 Information Provided to Users

The vast majority of repositories in our sample (88%), had a readily available, and easily identifiable mission statement on their website (see figure 9). However, the contents of the mission statements varied greatly. For some repositories, it was a short statement outlining the purpose of the repository and describing the data stored by the repository. Others had longer mission statements which provided additional information on areas such as the repository goal(s), data management policies and organisational hierarchy, amongst others.

There were no exclusion criteria for mission statements examined in the desk research as there is currently no agreed upon definition of what constitutes a mission statement. It is entirely possible for a repository to deliver its mission statement in either a single sentence or an entire page of information covering various aspects of the repository's practice. Thus, the existence of a mission statement may be of lesser interest compared to the information contained within the mission statement. That being said, all CESSDA, CLARIN and unaffiliated repositories in our sample had a mission statement compared to 70% of DARIAH, and 83% of E-RIHS repositories (see table 7). The authors did note further similarities between repository mission statements and ERIC membership in terms of both structural uniformity of the text and alignment of content, although an extensive analysis of repository mission statements and their content was beyond the scope of the desk research. Possible future work could include the examination of repository mission statements using content analysis. Such work is of import because

¹⁸ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2019.

¹⁹ CE-2013-0095: Checklist for CLARIN B Centres 2019.

²⁰ Hausstein & Horton 2020.

first impressions matter, and a mission statement is usually one of the first things users see on a repository's website. Certification status also appeared to influence the availability of mission statements for repositories in our sample, with all certified repositories having a mission statement, alongside 79% of uncertified repositories (see table 8).

Figure 9. Shares of repositories providing a mission statement, terms and conditions on data use, a model citation or citation guidelines, and stating that they are responsible for long-term preservation (n=93). Percentages were rounded up.

Terms and conditions for the re-use of data were provided by 75% of repositories in our sample. ERIC membership also appeared to influence the provision of terms and conditions for data (re)use, with only half of E-RIHS repositories, and just over two thirds of DARIAH repositories in our sample having such terms and conditions in place. This is compared to 80% of CESSDA repositories and 92% of CLARIN repositories, alongside 86% of unaffiliated repositories (see table 7). Similarly, 90% of the certified repositories provided terms and conditions for data (re)use compared with 64% of uncertified repositories in our sample.

63% of repositories in our sample provided model data citations and/or guidelines on how to cite the data. CESSDA repositories stood out in this regard, with nearly all CESSDA repositories in our sample providing model data citations and/or guidelines for citing data, compared to a smaller number of unaffiliated repositories and repositories affiliated with other ERICs (see table 7 below).

	CESSDA repositories (n=20)	CLARIN repositories (n=24)	DARIAH repositories (n=30)	E-RIHS repositories (n=12)	Unaffiliated repositories (n=7)
Percentage of repositories with a mission statement	100%	100%	70%	83%	100%
Percentage of repositories stating they provide long- term preservation	95%	75%	20%	33%	86%
Percentage of repositories with terms and conditions on data use	80%	92%	67%	50%	86%
Percentage of repositories with a model citation or citation guidelines	95%	63%	43%	58%	71%

Table 7. Breakdown of repositories by infrastructure membership in providing a mission statement, mentioning long-term preservation, having terms and conditions on data use, and providing a model citation or citation guidelines. Percentages were rounded up.

56% of repositories in our sample mentioned long-term digital preservation in some form or another, with long term digital preservation being frequently cited in preservation policies and/or in repository mission statements. Long-term digital preservation was mentioned by the majority of CESSDA, CLARIN and unaffiliated repositories (see table 7). Certification status also appeared to play a role in the discussion of long-term digital preservation, with 80% of certified repositories mentioning long-term digital preservation compared to 37% of uncertified repositories (see table 8). This is not overly surprising as only repositories offering long-term digital preservation are eligible for the CoreTrustSeal. This is reflected in Requirement 1 ('Mission/Scope') of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements where, to reach a Compliance Level of 3 or higher, the repository must address data preservation in their mission

statement.²¹ Having said that, it is possible to refer to digital preservation without mentioning preservation times which is one possible explanation as to why long-term digital preservation was not mentioned by *all* of the certified repositories in our sample.

	Certified (n=41)	Not certified (n=52)
Percentage of repositories with a mission statement	100%	79%
Percentage of repositories stating that they provide long-term preservation	80%	37%
Percentage of repositories with terms and conditions on data use	90%	64%
Percentage of repositories with a model citation or citation guidelines	76%	54%

Table 8. Shares of certified and non-certified repositories providing a mission statement, mentioning long-term preservation, having terms and conditions on data use, and providing a model citation or citation guidelines. Percentages were rounded up.

The results of the desk research clearly show that certified repositories are more likely to provide outward-facing information on their activities, digital preservation approach and data access and citation requirements compared to non-certified repositories. Our results also illustrate how certification coincides with ERIC membership, particularly in the case of CESSDA and CLARIN whose member repositories tend to provide a greater degree of information to users compared to repositories affiliated with DARIAH or E-RHIS (or who are otherwise unaffiliated with an ERIC).

²¹ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board 2019.

3. Discussion

The diverse nature of the SSH repositories included in our sample demonstrates that, despite most of them being domain-specific/specialist repositories, there is still a considerable degree of diversity between them in terms of their geographical location, host organisation, designated community, disciplines serviced and the types of data that they store. This diversity makes for a rich repository landscape that benefits the SSH community throughout Europe. However, the heterogeneous nature of repository characteristics can create challenges for certification as some repositories are better-equipped and more inclined than others to seek TDR certification using existing certification solutions.

TDR certification within the SSH community is heavily linked to ERIC membership, particularly for members of CESSDA and CLARIN. This is most likely the result of the expectations set by CESSDA and CLARIN regarding CoreTrustSeal certification and membership of their research infrastructure. The lack of certification among E-RIHS repositories is also notable. However, given E-RIHS is not expected to be fully operational until some time in 2022, only time will tell as to what effect E-RIHS membership will have on the certification status of its members in the long term.

Whilst the results presented in this report are unable to provide any significant insight into the reasons for the difference in certification status among the members of the four ERICs, the experiences gained from the SSHOC Task 8.2 certification support process do provide some insight. Possible reasons for the differing levels of certification among the members of the four ERICs include less awareness of the benefits of certification, a lack of necessary resources required to apply for assessment and certification, alongside the perceived difficulty in obtaining TDR certification. For cultural heritage repositories, the reason for lower levels of certification may also lie in the greater variability of repository characteristics, coupled with the specificity of the data types that they preserve. In the case of physical objects, for instance, the digital data being preserved might describe an original object. The digital data is therefore secondary and more akin to metadata, which means the repositories are more likely to devote more effort to preserving the original object rather than the digital one. On the other hand, within the field of social sciences and linguistics the data are digital by origin; thus, the requirements for the long-term preservation of such data align more directly with TDR certification requirements.

The names and URLs for most of the repositories in our sample appeared stable, although there were a number of repositories that had altered either their name and/or URL. Members of the SSHOC T8.2 team also noted difficulties in obtaining and verifying information relating to changes in repository name and/or URL. Such changes, and the difficulties in confirming such changes highlight the importance of repository best practice, particularly concerning information provision and documentation. When such changes are made it is vital to document processes and procedures and manage operations in a planned, coherent and transparent manner. It also highlights the importance of repository identifiers and repository registries.

The number of repositories in our sample that were listed on registries was at a reassuring level, albeit with some nuances relating to certification status and ERIC membership. CESSDA and CLARIN repositories were more likely to have re3data profiles, while DARIAH and E-RIHS repositories appeared to favour ROR. FAIRsharing stood out as a registry as only a few repositories in our sample had a FAIRsharing record. The discoverability of repositories could be improved by wider registry use amongst SSH repositories. Based on our results TDR certification could be a possible way of increasing registry use amongst repositories as certified repositories were more likely to have at least one repository registry records compared to non-certified repositories. However, ‘setting and forgetting’ a repository registry record is not enough; maintaining the record is just as important as creating it if users are to be provided with up-to-date and reliable information about a given repository and its services. Our results suggest that there is room for improvement when it comes to the maintenance of repository registry records (at least on re3data), in turn illustrating the need for a “coordinated systemic approach to professional management of registries”, as noted in the *Turning FAIR into reality* report²².

Many of the repositories in our sample maintained the discoverability of their data through the use of persistent identifiers. However, the number of repositories in our sample not using a PID system is still disconcertingly high, particularly in the era of FAIR data. The lack of PID use amongst our sample demonstrates that further work is needed to raise awareness on making data findable and accessible. The apparent link between PID use, TDR certification and ERIC membership suggests that research infrastructures and standards bodies could play a key role in increasing the update of PIDs within the SSH community.

On a more positive note, the results of this research suggest that information provision for users and other stakeholders is relatively well established amongst SSH repositories, although there is still room for improvement. There were notable differences between members of the different ERICs in terms of the structure and content of repository mission statements, information provided on approach to digital preservation, terms and conditions regarding the (re)use of data, and citation guidance. The link between ERIC membership and information provision can, at least in part, be explained by the certification status of the repositories in question, and the tendency for certified repositories in our sample to provide more complete information to users and other stakeholders.

²² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2018.

4. Conclusion

As the selection of repositories was purposive, the results reported here are not generalisable to the wider repository landscape in Europe. Nevertheless, this report, coupled with the report on the SSHOC survey²³ conducted by the Task T8.2 team, provides an overview of the diverse nature of the SSH community as well as an insight into a range of different issues affecting it. Our results suggest that both TDR certification and ERIC membership play key roles in improving repository practices. However, as most of the repositories in our sample were specialist/domain specific repositories, further work is needed to ascertain whether TDR certification and/or ERIC membership have a similar effect on generalist repository practice.

Furthermore, though TDR certification is one possible method of increasing the provision and availability of information held by, and relating to, repositories and their practice, certification may not be suitable for all digital repositories and wider data service providers, the latter of which may not even be eligible for TDR certification due to the nature of their organisations. Another possible solution would be for ERICs (and other research infrastructures) taking a more active role in the development of standards, particularly in relation to wider data service providers. However, the degree of influence that they could exert may change as both the research infrastructures and wider data services sector advances. The forthcoming SSHOC Task 8.2 Deliverable (D8.3) will discuss possible certification solutions for SSH repositories in more detail; the complex partnership models employed within the TDR community will also be examined alongside the sustainable management of trust.²⁴

Whilst this report serves as an opening gambit, it only scratches the surface by way of an examination of the issues facing the SSH community. Further quantitative and qualitative research is required to fully examine the large variety of data repositories operating within both the SSH and wider European repository landscape.

²³ Ala-Lahti et al. 2022.

²⁴ Kleemola et al. (forthcoming)

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6. Appendixes

Appendix 1: Characteristics Examined within the Desk Research

1. ID [given by T8.2]
2. Community
3. Repository name
4. Abbreviation
5. Host organisation
6. Country
7. Website
8. Has the repository name and URL changed since D8.2?
9. Link to re3data entry if it exists
10. re3data last updated
11. Link to fairsharing record if it exists
12. Link to ROR record if it exists
13. Repository type: CTS typology (Domain or subject-based repository; Institutional repository; National repository system, including governmental; Publication repository; Library/Museum/Archives; Research project repository; Other)
- 14 a. Is the repository coverage generalist or specialist?
- 14 b. Discipline/subject if specialist
15. Year the repository was established
16. Number of digital objects (e.g studies) in the repository holdings
17. Size of the repository in gigabytes
18. FTE of the repository

19. Does the repository have a mission statement / service promise? (Yes/no)
20. Link to service promise / mission of the repository if it exists
21. Paste the mission statement / service promise here
22. What is the repository's designated community?
23. Is the repository responsible for digital long-term preservation? (Yes/no)
24. Any additional remarks regarding preservation times?
25. Is the repository CTS-certified? (Yes/no)
26. List all other certifications/badges etc. that the repository has (e.g. ISO, FitSM, ITIL, national standards)
27. Description of types of data archived/stored by the repository
28. Link to an example of a metadata record if it exists (use PID if available)
29. PID system(s) used by the repository (ark, doi, handle, purl, urn, other)
30. Is there a model citation on the landing page that a researcher can use? (Yes/no)
- 31 a. Is there rights information? (Yes/no/not found). Note: this is about terms and conditions and rights about re-use of data communicated to users.
- 31 b. Link to rights information page(s)
32. Assessment on how much of the re3data was up to date (All or nearly all of it, Some of it, Very little or none of it)
33. Additional notes

Appendix 2: Categorisation of Terminology Repositories Used to Describe their Designated Communities

The terms were only altered when the term could lead to the identification of the repository who took part. Edited terms have been marked accordingly. The purpose of the table is not to prescribe a specific way of categorising members and entities within a designated community.

Category	Terms	Notes
Research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community • Research community • Scholars • Researchers • Subject-specific researchers • Subject-specific communities • [Subject specific] scholars • Scientists • Historians • [Subject-specific] scientists • Subject-specific historians • [Subject-specific] research communities • National researchers • Foreign researchers • Research institutions • Academic community • [National] scientific community 	<p>It is acknowledged that '<i>Scientists</i>' and '<i>[Subject-specific] scientists</i>' could include scientists that work for private enterprise and/or not be directly involved in research.</p> <p>It is also acknowledged that <i>Scientific community</i> could include individuals working within private enterprise, and private enterprises themselves, along with others.</p>
National Governments and Political Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political parties • [Political] members • Think-tanks • Government analysts • Policy makers 	
Private Enterprise / Corporations organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology developers • Producers of [discipline-specific] tools • Private companies 	
General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Local communities [within national populace] • Sub-communities [within a national population] • Descendants 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National community [all citizens] • [Genealogically specific community within the] International community • General audience • Citizens • Public 	
Educational Institutions, Staff and Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctoral candidates • Teachers • Students • [Subject/discipline-specific] students • Educational users • Educational institutions 	
Independent Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Discipline-specific] professionals • [Discipline specific] linguists • Linguists •Clinicians • Business consultants • Data analysts • Data professionals 	
Media Organisations and Journalists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Members of media • Journalists • Media professionals 	<p><i>'Journalists' were separated from 'independent professionals' category due to the specificity of their role and the number of mentions.</i></p> <p><i>'Media professionals' were included due to their relationship to journalists, although it is acknowledged that they may also include, for example, sound specialists, video editors, newspaper editors and so forth.</i></p>
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External partners • External institutions • Staff • Institutional members • Internal users • People and organizations • Others involved with [subject-specific] technology • Consumers of language tools • Users of [subject-specific] materials • [Specific] technological communities 	<p>The terms listed in this category could not be placed within any of the above categories due to their ambiguity.</p> <p><i>'Financiers' included in this category as term could refer to research funders or private organisations funding, for example, development of tools or commercial research. à None of the repositories included in the sample mentioned 'funders' as a designated community.</i></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Independent research centres• Data Archives• Financiers	<p><i>'Data archives'</i> included in this category as archives can exist within a multitude of sectors including the public and private research sectors, government and educational institutions, amongst others.</p>
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